

Hierarchical self-assembly of a new guanosine derivative to quadruplex structure in presence of potassium and ytterbium ions

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Substituted guanosine molecules can form nanostructures through self-assembly in presence of alkali metal ions in lipophilic solvents. Most of the cases the assembly is directed by the H-bonding interaction as well as the interaction of alkali metal ion with the guanosine molecules. Herein we report the synthesis of a new bipyridyl substituted guanosine molecule G5 which forms a tris bipyridyl ruthenium complex G5-Ru which has been characterized by ESI-MS as well as NMR spectroscopy. This ruthenium complex G5-Ru forms a quadruplex self-assembly in presence of potassium picrate and ytterbium triflate in acetone which has been detected by CD spectroscopy as well as ESI-MS studies in case of ytterbium triflate.

Keywords: Guanosine, noncovalent interaction, Ru-complex, ytterbium triflate.

Introduction

Non-covalent bond is a powerful tool in the construction of supramolecular architecture. The ability to utilize such dynamic bonds to impart tunable and responsive properties on the resulting aggregates has led to the dramatic growth of this field of supramolecular chemistry by self-assembly¹. The nature of such self-assembled products has a strong dependence on not only the components they are constituted from but also on the type of interactions present among those components. The wealth of the supramolecular bonds that molecules use to interact with each other and their subtle interplay make this field so promising. A biologically relevant assembly that lends itself well to synthetic supramolecular study is the G-quartet, which is a H-bonded structure composed of four Hoogsteen-paired guanine bases². Guanine-rich sequences are abundant in telomeric ends of chromosomes and promoter regions of DNA and are capable of forming G-quartets *in vitro*³. Guanine self-assembly in lipophilic systems has been the focus of much research in the past and has been reviewed in detail⁴. Several synthetic hydrophilic unimolecular G-quartet assemblies have been reported⁶. G-quartets are typically templated and stabilized by cations⁷, whereas guanine aggregation in the absence of cations generally results in the formation of ribbon like structures⁸. The existence of these ribbon like structures both in

solution and solid states is now well established. The importance of this ribbon like architectures has been demonstrated in designing the molecular electronic devices by Spada and coworkers⁹. In all these cases functionalized guanosine derivatives have been synthesized and the H-bonded assembly resulted into the supramolecular ribbon like polymers in non-H-bonding solvents (e.g. chloroform, dichloromethane etc.). The G-quadruplex structures which are usually self-assembled in presence of alkali metal ions and alkaline earth metal ions in lipophilic solvents have been found to form nice tetrameric nanostructures as observed through AFM and STM¹⁰. These artificial G-quadruplex nanostructures have been successfully used in several biomimetic applications¹⁰.

Although there are couple of reports on the formation of quadruplex structures by the substituted guanosine molecules the formation of hierarchical assembly involving both the H-bonding and metal-ligand co-ordination bonding approach has not been studied with guanosine derivatives. Herein we report the synthesis of a new guanosine derivative G5 (Scheme 1) which forms complex G5-Ru with *cis*-bis(2,2'-bipyridine)dichlororuthenium(II) hydrate. The major advantage of incorporation of the ruthenium into the guanine structure is that after the final assembly this ruthenium substitution may act as photo switch for the photo-chemical application of the final assembly. More over the use of the lanthanide

ions for the assembly of G-quadruplex structure have been demonstrated recently where the incorporation of the Eu^{3+} and Tb^{3+} ions have contributed to the luminescent behavior of the resulting assembly¹¹. The complex G5-Ru self-assembles in presence of potassium picrate and ytterbium triflate to form the quadruplex structures which have been confirmed by CD spectra as well as ESI-MS studies.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of the guanosine derivative G5 was accomplished as stated in Scheme 1. Compound **3** was synthesized according to the synthetic scheme and was characterized by the ^1H NMR spectroscopy as shown in Fig. S1. Reaction of 3-bromo 2,2'-bipyridyl with ethynyl trimethyl silane followed by hydrolysis results in the synthesis of 3-alkynyl 2,2'-bipyridine (**1**) which was completely characterized by the ^1H as well as ^{13}C NMR (Figs. S2 and S3). This was then reacted with 8-bromo-2',3'-*o*-isopropylidene guanosine **3** in DMF under sonogasira coupling conditions to get the product G5. Formation of new guanosine substituent G5 has been confirmed by proton, ^{13}C and ESI mass spectrometry.

The ^1H NMR shows all the respective peaks for the compound G5 where the aromatic protons of the bipyridyl substituent come between 8.75 to 7.5 ppm. The peak at 11 ppm can be attributed to the NH proton of the guanosine residue

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the guanosine derivative G5.

Fig. 1. ^1H NMR of G5 recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$.

whereas peak at 6.75 ppm can be assigned as the NH₂ proton of the guanosine residue. The ESI-MS spectra shown in Fig. S4 clearly depicts the formation of the G5 with the [M+H]⁺ ion peak at 502.

To form the hierarchical self-assembly of newly designed guanosine substituent G5 we first reacted G5 with *cis*-ruthenium bis-bipyridyl chloride in dry and degassed ethanol under nitrogen atmosphere (Scheme 2) for 24–30 h and then the pure orange colored tris-bipyridyl complex G5-Ru was precipitated out from the reaction mixture by the addition of excess ammonium hexafluorophosphate. G5-Ru was characterized by proton NMR, ESI-MS and elemental analysis. In proton NMR (Fig. 2) the two possible stereoisomers (Λ and Δ) of G5-Ru appears at different chemical shift positions which is common for tris-bipyridyl ruthenium complexes¹².

The DOSY NMR in Fig. S5 also shows the appearance of the two stereoisomers (Λ and Δ) with the same diffusion

coefficient which is explicable from the point of same size of the two different stereoisomers and hence having the same diffusion coefficients.

However the LCMS spectrum (Fig. S6) of G5-Ru shows a single product as the mass of both the stereoisomers would be the same.

The formation of quadruplex assembly of G5-Ru in the presence of potassium ion was performed by reacting the G5-Ru complex with potassium picrate in acetone solution. The product was isolated by precipitation with ether addition. The formation of the G-quadruplex assembly is usually monitored by CD spectroscopy¹³. The left of Fig. 3 shows the CD spectra of the G5-Ru complex before reaction with potassium picrate and after reaction with 10⁻³ M potassium picrate solution in acetone. The characteristic signal at 280 nm and the 300 nm in the CD spectra indicates the formation of a quadruplex structure¹³.

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectra of G5-Ru in acetone-*d*₆.

Scheme 2. The schematic representation of formation of a hierarchical self-assembly by bipyridyl guanosine.

The formation of the quadruplex structure by G5-Ru in presence of the lanthanide $\text{Yb}(\text{SO}_3\text{CF}_3)_3$ was also investigated by CD spectroscopy and the right hand side of the Fig. 3 shows the CD spectra of the G5-Ru complex in acetone with and without the presence of ytterbium triflate. In presence of $25 \mu\text{M}$ ytterbium triflate the peak appears at 280 and 300 nm respectively corresponding to the formation of the quadruplex structure. The formation of the quadruplex assembly was also investigated by ESI-MS (Fig. 4) in case of ytterbium triflate. The presence of the peak at 10102 corresponding to the M^+ of $[\text{G5-Ru}]_8[\text{PF}_6]_{16}\text{Yb}(\text{SO}_3\text{CF}_3)_3$ clearly indicate the formation of the quadruplex assembly in presence of the Yb^{3+} .

However the formation of quadruplex assembly by potassium picrate was not monitored by ESI-MS.

Conclusion

We have successfully synthesized a new bipyridyl substituted guanosine derivative G5 which forms a ruthenium complex G5-Ru by reaction with *cis*-bis(2,2'-bipyridine)dichlororuthenium(II) hydrate. The ruthenium complex of the new guanosine derivative G5-Ru self-assembles in the presence of potassium and ytterbium ions to form the quadruplex structures which have been confirmed by CD spectroscopy as well as ESI-MS studies. The assembly of G5-Ru in presence of lanthanide ion Yb^{3+} may have interesting optoelectronic properties. The photo induced electron transfer from the Ru center to lanthanide upon excitation at the MLCT absorption band of Ru^{II} can make this an extremely valuable material towards solar energy conversion which is being under investigation.

Fig. 3. CD spectra of the formation of hierarchical self-assembly with G5-Ru in presence of K^+ and Yb^{3+} ions.

Fig. 4. ESI-MS of the $[G5-Ru]_8[PF_6]_{16}Yb[SO_3CF_3]_3$ showing the M^+ at 10102.

Experimental

Materials, methods and instrumentation:

1H NMR, ^{13}C and DOSY NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance 400 or Bruker Avance 500 spectrometers. CHN analysis was performed on a Perkin-Elmer, USA model No. 2400 Series 2. Mass spectrometric (ESI and LCMS) analysis was performed on a LCT Premier mass spectrophotometer. CD spectroscopy was performed on a JASCO J-1000 spectrometer with the solution of the G5-Ru complex in acetone along with potassium picrate 10^{-3} M solution or ytterbium triflate (25 μ M in acetone). All chemicals and

deuterated solvents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich chemical company and were used without any further purification.

Synthesis of 2-ethynyl-2,2'-bipyridine 1:

To a stirred suspension of 2-bromo-2,2'-bipyridine (500 mg, 2.12 mmol), bis-diphenylphosphine palladium chloride (701.91 mg, 0.21 mmol) and cuprous iodide (30 mg, 0.21 mmol) in 20 ml dry tetrahydrofuran was added trimethyl silyl acetylene (0.7 ml, 4.8 mmol) under nitrogen. Then to this stirred mixture under nitrogen was added 10 ml dry triethylamine and this was kept for stirring at 65°C overnight. After

18 h solvent was removed from the dark brown solution under reduced pressure and the brown residue was charged on a alumina column. The pure trimethyl silyl substituted product was isolated from the alumina column by eluting with 30% ethyl acetate in hexane. ^1H NMR in CDCl_3 : δ 8.69 (d, 1H, bpy), 8.49 (d, 1H, bpy), 8.37 (d, 1H, bpy), 7.8 (m, 2H, bpy), 7.51 (d, 1H, bpy), 7.33 (d, 1H, bpy), 0.33 (s, 9H, tms) ppm.

To the mixture of trimethyl silyl alkynyl bipyridine (600 mg, 2.38 mmol) and potassium carbonate (722 mg, 5.23 mmol) under nitrogen was added dry methanol 100 ml and the resulting suspension was kept for stirring under nitrogen overnight. After 16 h solvent was removed and the yellowish white residue was extracted with dichloromethane. Washing the dichloromethane part with water and drying the organic part over anhydrous sodium sulphate followed by the removal of solvent under reduced pressure gave the pure compound **1** in 70% yield. ^1H NMR in CDCl_3 : δ 8.7 (d, 1H, bpy), 8.52 (d, 1H, bpy), 8.42 (d, 1H, bpy), 7.83 (m, 2H, bpy), 7.53 (d, 1H, bpy), 7.36 (d, 1H, bpy), 3.22 (s, 1H, alkynyl) ppm; ^{13}C NMR in CDCl_3 : δ 156.62, 155.22, 149.22, 141.53, 136.95, 127.65, 123.98, 121.4, 120.95, 83.08, 76.83 ppm; ESI-MS m/z Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\cdot\text{H}^+$ [M+H] $^+$ 181.21, Found 181.

Synthesis of compound **2**:

To a stirred suspension of guanosine (2 g, 7.06 mmol) in acetone was added HClO_4 (0.9 ml, 10 mmol) and the suspension became clear solution. This solution was then stirred for 70 min and then NH_4OH was added dropwise with a white precipitate coming out of the solution. This precipitate was filtered and dried under vacuum to give a white crystalline solid. Yield 80%. ^1H NMR in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$: δ 8.6 (br, 1H, N^{H}), 7.93 (s, 1H, H_8), 6.5 (brs, 2H, $\text{N}^{2\text{H}}$), 5.9 (d, 1H, H_1'), 5.2 (dd, 1H, H_2'), 4.97 (dd, 1H, H_3'), 4.15–4.10 (m, 1H, H_4'), 3.56–3.52 (m, 2H, H_5' , H_5''), 1.53 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.33 (s, 3H, CH_3) ppm; ^{13}C NMR in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$: δ 157.21 (C6), 154.15 (C2), 151.20 (C4), 136.35 (C8), 117.19 (C5), 113.51, 88.91, 87.11, 84.04, 81.65, 62.08, 27.53, 25.70 ppm.

Synthesis of 8-bromo guanosine **3**:

To a stirred suspension of **2** (800 mg, 2.47 mmol) in acetonitrile was added N-bromo succinimide (794 mg, 4.46 mmol) in three portions and the resulting yellow suspension was kept under stirring for another one hour. After one hour the yellow reaction mixture was centrifuged. Addition of diethyl ether to the centrifugate resulted in the formation of

white precipitate which was centrifuged and washed thrice with diethyl ether. Then the white residue was chromatographed on a silica gel column using 1–10% of methanol in chloroform. The resulting compound was isolated as a slightly yellow powder in 60% yield. ^1H NMR in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$: δ 10.9 (s, 1H, NH), 6.7 (broad singlet, 2H, NH_2), 5.9 (s, 1H, sugar), 5.5 (dd, 1H, sugar), 5.2 (dd, 1H, sugar), 4.7 (t, 1H, OH), 4.1 (m, 1H, sugar), 3.5 (m, 2H), 1.5 (s, 3H, methyl), 1.3 (s, 3H, methyl) ppm; ^{13}C $\text{DMSO}-d_6$: δ 156.16, 154.03, 151.86, 120.64, 117.57, 113.55, 90.13, 88.99, 83.49, 81.83, 62.3, 27.54, 25.82 ppm; ESI-MS m/z Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{BrN}_5\text{O}_5\cdot\text{H}^+$ [M+H] $^+$ 402.03, Found 402.

Synthesis of **G5**:

8-Bromo guanosine (100 mg, 0.248 mmol), 2-ethynyl-2,2'-bipyridine (53.46 mg, 0.297 mmol), tetrakis(triphenyl phosphine palladium (17 mg, 0.014 mmol), cuprous iodide (7 mg, 0.03 mmol), triethyl amine (5 ml) were combined in dry DMF (10 ml) and stirred under argon at 70°C for 18 h. After that the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in chloroform and washed with saturated EDTA solution. The organic layer was dried over magnesium sulphate and removal of the solvent gave a brown solid. This was chromatographed on a alumina column with 1–10% of methanol in chloroform. The resulting compound was obtained as yellowish white solid in 40% yield. ^1H NMR in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$: δ 11.3 (brs, 1H, NH), 8.75 (d, 1H, bpy), 8.49 (d, 1H, bpy), 8.43 (d, 1H, bpy), 8.11 (m, 1H, bpy), 7.99 (m, 1H, bpy), 7.83 (d, 1H, bpy), 7.5 (m, 1H, bpy), 7.2 (brs, 2H, NH_2), 6.15 (s, 1H, sugar), 5.49 (m, 1H, sugar), 5.29 (m, 1H, sugar), 5.02 (m, 1H, OH), 4.11 (m, 1H, sugar), 3.6 (m, 2H, sugar), 1.57 (s, 3H, Me), 1.35 (s, 3H, Me) ppm; ESI-MS m/z Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_7\text{O}_5\cdot\text{H}^+$ [M+H] $^+$ 502.18, Found 502.

Synthesis of **G5-Ru**:

Dry and degassed ethanol (20 ml) was added to a mixture of **G5** (50 mg, 0.1 mmol) and $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{Cl}_2$ (59 mg, 0.11 mmol) under nitrogen and the resulting brownish red solution was kept under reflux for 30 h. After 30 h the solution became orange red and excess ammonium hexafluorophosphate was added to the solution. A deep orange colored precipitate started to appear. The precipitate was filtered and washed with ethanol and ether. Yield 87%. ^1H NMR in $\text{Acetone}-d_6$: δ 10.5 and 9.7 (1H, NH), 9–7 (22H, aromatic H), 7.06 and 6.86 (1H, aromatic H), 6.52 and 6.44 (2H, NH_2), 5.68 and 5.53 (1H, sugar 1'H), 5.40 and 5.13 (1H, sugar

2'H), 5.21 and 5.01 (1H, sugar 3'H), 4.84 and 4.24 (1H, OH), 4.35 and 4.07 (1H, sugar 4'H), 3.73–3.59 (2H, sugar 5'H), 1.54–1.27 (6H, CH₃) ppm; ESI-MS for C₄₅H₃₉F₁₂N₁₁O₅P₂Ru: (M⁺) Calcd. 1059, Found 1060; (M²⁺) Calcd. 457, Found 458. Elemental analysis for C₄₅H₃₉F₁₂N₁₁O₅P₂Ru.4H₂O: Calcd. C, 42.33; H, 3.71; N, 12.07. Found: C, 42.42; H, 3.32; N, 11.58.

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